

Spatiotemporal Assessment of Artificial Night Light and Its Potential Impact on Amphibian Habitats in the Indian Sundarbans Using Remote Sensing and GIS

Tazmin Sultana¹, Soumyadip Dewanji²

DOI:

Abstract: The Indian Sundarbans is a UNESCO World Heritage Site and mangrove biosphere reserve covering approximately 26,000 km² across 104 islands, representing one of the most diverse ecosystems globally, harboring 8 amphibian species, 49 mammal species, 59 reptile species, 210+ fish species, and 260+ bird species. This region is home to more than 4.5 million people in fragmented settlements, driving infrastructure development, including extensive lighting systems. Amphibians, among the most light-sensitive organisms, face unprecedented exposure to artificial night light (ANL), but the spatiotemporal dynamics of ANL expansion and its impacts on amphibian habitats remain unexplored. This study explores the spatial and temporal distribution of ANL and its potential effects on amphibian habitats using GIS and remote sensing. VIIRS-DNB nighttime light data from 2013–2023 were processed through Google Earth Engine to derive annual mean radiance and extract light intensity changes. Sentinel-2 satellite imagery was classified to map key habitat components: mangroves, wetlands, and built-up areas. Amphibian occurrence data from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) were collected and assessed habitat suitability by integrating vegetation indices, elevation, and distance to water bodies. This analysis combined ANL intensity maps with habitat suitability surfaces and amphibian presence zones to identify high-illumination regions within critical amphibian habitats. Results are expected to reveal increasing light intensity near settlements, roads, and tourism areas, potentially disrupting amphibian activity and breeding patterns. The study identifies sensitive zones for dark-sky management and targeted amphibian conservation interventions in these mangrove ecosystems.

Keywords: artificial night light, amphibian habitats, VIIRS, Sundarbans

Corresponding Author: stazmin2145@gmail.com

¹ Environment and Disaster Management, Ramakrishna Mission Vivekananda Educational and Research Institute, India

² Bachelor of Dental Surgery, Guru Nanak Institute of Dental Sciences and Research, India